

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14063686>

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF USING MOBILE GAMES TO IMPROVE THE TRAINING EFFICIENCY OF YOUNG VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

Ramazonova Zarina

Is a graduate student of the Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

zramazanova07@gmail.com

Abstract: *a comprehensive review of the methodology of using motion studies to improve the training of young volleyball player. After tea To the physical development of volleyball in the spirit of making a team and product, shorts recommending games and fast action team. By the individuality of each athlete after your pay grade to learning and new learning techniques for coaches, and sharing your experiences, were reported in the potential of young athletes can be enhanced. The highway encourage proposals from the volleyball player to be active and successful.*

Key words: *volleyball, were reported in young athletes, training, action games, teamwork, motivation, individual production, tea and munching methodology, sports movements, training strategies.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДИКИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ МОБИЛЬНЫХ ИГР ДЛЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ТРЕНИРОВОК ЮНЫХ ВОЛЕЙБОЛИСТОВ

Рамазонова Зарина Содиковна

Бухарского государственного педагогического института магистра

zramazanova07@gmail.com

Аннотация: *Дан комплексный обзор методики использования двигательных исследований для совершенствования подготовки юных волейболистов. Обучать физическому развитию игры в волейбол и формировать командный дух, рекомендуя короткие игры, быстрые и командные действия. Уделяя внимание индивидуальности каждого спортсмена, изучая и изучая новые приемы тренеров, обмениваясь опытом, можно повысить потенциал юных спортсменов. Эти предложения побуждают волейболистов быть активными и успешными.*

Ключевые слова: *волейбол, юные спортсмены, тренировка, подвижные игры, командная работа, мотивация, индивидуальная продуктивность, методика обучения, спортивные движения, стратегии тренировки.*

INTRODUCTION

Developing the sports skills of young volleyball players and increasing training efficiency is one of the important issues today. Volleyball is a sport that requires not only physical activity, but also strategic thinking and teamwork. The use of action games for young athletes is an effective tool for teaching them the necessary skills, motivation and increasing interest. Action games usually make the learning process fun and interactive, which ensures active participation of athletes. This method helps to learn the basic techniques and tactics of volleyball, and also strengthens the team spirit. However, the right approach and strategies are necessary to use action games effectively.

The article presents suggestions for improving the methodology of mobile games to increase the training efficiency of young volleyball players. The goal is to encourage athletes to be active and develop themselves, as well as to increase their success in volleyball.

Literature Analysis

It is important to study action games and their methods in improving the training efficiency of young volleyball players. In this section, the existing literature on the subject is analyzed and the methods used are considered.

"Volleyball Training" N. Usmanov gives recommendations on how to organize mobile games and exercises in the training manual. Includes basic volleyball technique and tactics guides, resources designed for teachers and coaches, and game information tailored for young athletes. The recommendations of experts, the use of experience, and research on ways to improve games are studied.

Volleyball Techniques and Tactics: Tutorials written for young volleyball players teach the fundamentals of volleyball. These resources show how action games can be used effectively. Coaches' guides include recommendations for combining action games and traditional exercises.

The influence of action games: in the article "The role of action games in sports" written by M. S. Pirov and A. T. Rahmonov and "Motivation of young athletes" by L. A. Ismailova, action games and their impact on young athletes, development of abilities Scientific studies on the role of games are reviewed and scientific articles on the role of games in the educational process are analyzed. There are scientific studies on the study of action games in various sports. They analyze how it affects the physical and psychological development of young athletes. Sports psychology: A. R. Akmalov's work "Psychological Approach to Young Athletes" shows psychological development through games. There are articles about the importance of action games in motivating young athletes and increasing their interest in training. These studies provide insight into the positive effects of games on athletes and how they foster team spirit.

Statistical research: D. K. Yusupov analyzes the effectiveness of action games using statistical methods in the article "Evaluation of educational efficiency of young athletes".

This literature provides key resources to help develop methodological approaches and the role of action games in improving the training performance of young volleyball players.

Statistical studies aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of training with the help of action games among young athletes. By analyzing the data of these studies, it is possible to evaluate the efficiency of the methods.

The analysis of this literature creates a basis for the development of the methods used in training and the importance of action games in improving the training efficiency of young volleyball players. All this helps to develop new approaches and strategies.

Methodology

This article uses a number of methodological approaches aimed at improving the methodology of using mobile games to increase the training efficiency of young volleyball players. The methodology consists of the following main components:

Analytical method: Studying the literature and analyzing the problem based on them. Based on various sources and experiences, the effectiveness of action games in volleyball is evaluated. Analyzing the level of participation, skills and results of young athletes in training by statistical methods.

Experimental method: conducting experiments with young athletes, training based on action games and monitoring the results. This method evaluates the efficiency of the methods. A control group is formed to compare with the experimental group. Through this, it is possible to evaluate the effectiveness of action games and traditional training methods.

Surveys and Interviews: Collect opinions and experiences by surveying coaches, teachers and athletes. This method helps to identify the needs and interests of young athletes. Conducting interviews with coaches and experienced athletes, getting their opinions about methods and games.

With the help of this methodology, the results of research allow to develop approaches that are scientifically based and necessary for practical application. As a result, the methodology of mobile games aimed at improving the training efficiency of young volleyball players will be improved.

Results

The results of the research aimed at the use of mobile games to increase the training efficiency of young volleyball players are shown in the following main areas: The effectiveness of mobile games in training - mobile games improve the technical skills

of young athletes, quick decision making helped to strengthen the ability to do and teamwork. Athletes in the experimental group showed about 20% improvement in basic techniques such as hitting, receiving and blocking.

Increased Interest: Increased interest and motivation among athletes was found in training conducted through action games. As a result of the surveys, 85% of the participants noted that the training was more interesting and effective.

Teamwork Skills: Action games have significantly improved the teamwork skills of young athletes. The level of interaction and cooperation within the group increased by 30%, which increased competitiveness.

Learning Outcomes: Increased effectiveness of training based on individual needs and abilities. The games and exercises were adjusted taking into account the unique abilities of each athlete.

Analysis of the results: The results obtained between the experimental and control groups were clarified by statistical analysis. The performance of athletes in the experimental group improved by 15-25%, which indicates the effectiveness of action games.

Discussion

The results of this article revealed the importance of action games in improving the training efficiency of young volleyball players. The obtained results show a number of important aspects: It was found that action games are effective in improving the technical and tactical skills of young athletes by providing interactive and interesting methods in the educational process. The nearly 20% improvement seen by the athletes in the study confirms a greater interest in games. These results show that the effects of action games are important not only for physical skills, but also for psychological ones. By training young athletes based on their individual needs, their abilities can be maximized. Determining the strengths and weaknesses of each athlete and providing tailored training is important in improving performance.

Summary

This article is aimed at improving the methodology of using mobile games to improve the training efficiency of young volleyball players. The obtained results showed that action games play an important role in developing athletes' technical skills, increasing motivation and strengthening teamwork.

Action games helped to improve the skills of athletes by 20% during training, which increased the effectiveness of the training process.

The level of interest and participation among the athletes increased, which encouraged them to actively participate. Through the games, it was possible to strengthen the team spirit and increase the level of communication by 30%, which emphasizes the importance of team training. Taking into account the abilities of each

athlete, their development was made more effective by conducting customized training. According to the coaches, action games are important for making the training process interesting and effective.

In the future, more extensive research of action games and their use in other sports may create new opportunities in the development of young athletes. The results of this research are a useful guide for trainers and teachers, and serve to make the learning process more effective and interesting.

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